

VERIFICATION OF THE EUROPEAN SEISMIC RISK MODEL (ESRM20)

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Abstract

A European seismic risk model will be released in 2020 as an output of the European Horizon 2020 SERA project (www.sera-eu.org), building also upon the research efforts of many previous projects (e.g. LESSLOSS, SYNER-G, NERA, SHARE). The main risk metrics that will be released with the model include national and sub-national maps of average annual loss (AAL) and probable maximum loss (PML) and national loss exceedance curves for 46 countries in Europe. Before the release of this model, the performance of its components needs to be extensively evaluated through a number of different tests.

This paper provides a brief summary of the current development of the ESRM20 and describes the testing framework that is being set up for the testing of the model. This framework leverages software development and includes unit tests, integration tests, system tests and acceptance tests. Unit tests consider the components of the risk model separately, whereas integration tests check the performance of a group of components together. Example integration tests include history checks where the total losses (fatalities and economic losses) estimated from all events in the European earthquake catalogue since 1980 will be undertaken, and comparisons will be made with the total observed losses and empirically derived annual average losses and loss exceedance curves (with the losses adjusted to today's value). To constrain the ground motion in the previous test, ShakeMaps for the historical events over the aforementioned period are being used to predict the damage/losses/consequences using the 'Scenario from ShakeMap' calculator of the OpenQuake-engine and these are being compared with the reported numbers in loss databases. More detailed verification tests are also being made for events in Italy and Greece for which detailed damage data at the building-by-building level is available.

Once the ESRM20 model is released, its components could then be submitted for prospective testing in a new testing centre that is being set up as part of the Horizon 2020 RISE project.

Keywords: seismic risk, loss assessment, testing, damage data, loss databases

1. Introduction

A European seismic risk model will be released in October 2020 (ESRM20) as an output of the European Horizon 2020 SERA project (www.sera-eu.org), building upon research efforts of many previous projects (e.g. LESSLOSS, SYNER-G, NERA, SHARE). The main risk metrics that will be released with the model include national and sub-national maps of average annual loss (AAL) and probable maximum loss (PML) and national loss exceedance curves for 46 countries in Europe. The 'Probabilistic Event-based Risk' calculator of the OpenQuake-engine [1, 2] is being used for all hazard and risk calculations of the European seismic risk model. Before the release of this model its performance will need to be extensively evaluated through a number of different tests that are outlined in this paper. It is noted that the focus herein is on the exposure, vulnerability and risk results of ESRM20 and does not cover the tests that are also being carried out during the development of the seismic hazard model.

2. European Seismic Risk Model (ESRM20)

For completeness, a brief summary of the current status of development of all components of ESRM20 is provided below, and then the testing framework for the risk components is outlined in the following sections.

2.1 Seismic Hazard

The first effort to develop a transparent, reproducible, consensus model of seismic hazard at the European scale was undertaken from 2008 to 2012 in the FP7 SHARE project (www.share-eu.org). This model was released as the 2013 European Seismic Hazard Model (ESHM13) [3] through an open platform (<http://www.efehr.org/en/Documentation/specific-hazard-models/>) through which all of the input data used to develop the model, the calculation input files and the hazard outputs were shared. This model is now being updated through the Horizon 2020 SERA project (www.sera-eu.org) and is currently at the alpha version stage. The beta version of this model will be developed by March 2020, and a final model is expected in October 2020 (ESHM20).

Seismic hazard models are comprised of two main components: seismogenic source models and ground motion models. The ESHM20 seismogenic source models are being developed using updates to the datasets used in ESHM13, namely the European Earthquake Catalogue and the European Database of Seismogenic Faults (EDSF). The models are combined in a logic tree which has two main branches: area source model (AS) and seismicity and faults (SEIFA). The uncertainty in the slope (b) and intercept (a) of each magnitude-frequency distribution (MFD) is being considered in the area source model branch of the logic tree together with the maximum magnitude uncertainty, whereas the MFD slope, fault slip rate and maximum magnitude uncertainties are considered in the SEIFA branch. The relative weights of the two main branches of the logic tree are still under discussion.

The ESHM13 ground motion models were combined through a logic tree using the most common approach at the time, i.e. the branches were populated with a selection of previously published GMPEs that were deemed appropriate for each tectonic environment. As discussed in [4], the epistemic uncertainty in the logic tree should vary geographically with higher values found in areas with limited data and lower uncertainty in areas with considerable data. Whilst this behaviour was seen in the ESHM13 model, a comparison of that model with site-specific studies at a number of locations across Europe showed lower fractiles of uncertainty in ESHM13. A more transparent approach to modelling the epistemic uncertainty in the ground motion model, which also ensures that all branches are mutually exclusive and collectively exhaustive, makes use of a so-called backbone approach. This approach has been used in many site-specific studies, in particular for critical facilities [5]. In this approach a single ground-motion model is scaled up or down to account for uncertainty in the median motion, where the scaling factors relate to the main sources of modelling uncertainty, such as average stress drop and anelastic attenuation. This approach has been adopted for the ESHM20 ground motion logic tree, with the backbone model being initially proposed by [4] and then modified during implementation to the final model.

An efficient and practical approach to incorporate site amplification into the ground-motion modelling of regional risk models uses topography to infer the 30-m averaged shear-wave velocity, V_{S30} (e.g. [6]), a parameter that is arguably the most widely used to represent site amplification in existing ground-motion models. However, given that V_{S30} is still just a proxy for site amplification, an investigation was undertaken within the SERA project to understand whether it performs better than using topographic slope or other proxies directly as parameters of the ground-motion model (see [7, 8]). For this purpose, a harmonised European geological map has thus also been required, and this has been developed using the maps from OneGeology (<http://europe-geology.eu/metadata>) and the European funded ProMine project (<http://promine.gtk.fi>). The ground motion model being developed for shallow crustal regions in Europe [9] has been rederived using geological unit and slope as parameters of a simple linear amplification function [8]. Figure 1 shows a comparison of the uncertainties in this ground motion model depending on the method used to model site amplification. This figure shows that the resulting aleatory uncertainty when using inferred V_{S30} and using slope directly are virtually identical and that the incorporation of geology does have a notable reduction on ϕ_s at spectral periods longer than approximately 0.5 s both for the slope and the inferred V_{S30} model.

Fig. 1 – Aleatory uncertainty on the site amplification function, ϕ_s (left), and the total variability, σ_T (right), of the ground motion model [9] for the different predictor variables when geology is excluded from the regression (dashed lines) and when it is included (solid lines).

2.2 Exposure

The development of an exposure model for ESRM20, i.e. the spatial distribution of the residential, commercial and industrial building count, population, and replacement cost - characterized in terms of building classes - follows two main steps (see e.g. [10]): i) identification of the predominant building classes within a given country that represent residential, commercial and industrial buildings, ii) modelling of the spatial distribution of the number of buildings, replacement cost and number of occupants within each building class across a given country, by combining a number of different publicly available datasets.

The buildings in the exposure model are classified according to their seismic performance using a building taxonomy that is based on an updated version of an international standard (the GEM Building Taxonomy, as updated by [11]) that allows buildings to be classified according to a number of structural attributes. The main attributes that have been selected for the consistent definition of building classes across Europe are as follows: main construction material (reinforced concrete, unreinforced masonry, reinforced/confined masonry, adobe, steel, timber); lateral load resisting system, LLRS (infilled frame, moment frame, wall, dual frame-wall system, flat slab/plate or waffle slab, post and beam); number of storeys; seismic design code level (CDN: pre-code, CDL: low code, CDM: moderate code, CDH: high code); and lateral load coefficient used in the seismic design.

The building classes in each country have been identified from local expert judgment, workshops and peer-reviewed publications, and then the population, building count and replacement cost in each country was distributed across these building classes. The main sources of input include the latest national housing censuses, socio-economic indicators (e.g. labor force, population and floor area per worker per economic sector), and mapping schemes (also referred to as inference rules) developed by the SERA project partners together with local experts. Development versions of the European Exposure Model (with increasing levels of detail) are being distributed through a public GitLab repository¹ up until the release of the v1.0 model in October 2020. Interactive viewers and map web services of the European exposure maps are also being released (see <https://maps.eu-risk.eucentre.it/>).

2.3 Vulnerability

The methodology employed by the Global Earthquake Model for their Global Seismic Risk Map (v2018.1) [12] has been applied as an initial set of fragility models for all building classes in Europe (see [13]). The following steps have been applied to develop the fragility models for European building classes with the GEM methodology:

- The structural and dynamic properties of each building class have been collected to produce capacity curves (e.g. yield and ultimate drifts, elastic and yield period of the first mode of vibration, participation factor of the first mode of vibration, common failure mechanisms). These attributes were collected from the literature (e.g. numerical studies, experimental tests, damage observations), and further adjusted based on expert judgment.
- Representative equivalent single-degree-of-freedom (SDOF) oscillators were developed for each building class.
- A database of ground motion records has been compiled for the nonlinear dynamic analyses using records with PGA above 0.05g and a maximum scaling factor of 2.
- Nonlinear dynamic analyses were performed (using OpenSees [14]) to evaluate the structural response (i.e. engineering demand parameter (EDP), taken as the maximum displacement) of the SDOF oscillators against the selected ground motion records.
- The cloud methodology is applied to define a best fit curve between the intensity measure level (IM) and an engineering demand parameter (EDP) in the logarithmic space. A censored regression approach was followed with the threshold for the censored observations being set at 1.5 times the displacement for the complete damage state. A number of different intensity measures have been considered in the regression, in particular spectral ordinates for different periods of vibration as well as average spectral acceleration, AvgSa, which is the geometric mean of a range of spectral ordinates.
- In order to calculate the probability of exceeding a set of damage states (DS2: slight, DS3: moderate, DS4: extensive and DS4: complete damage), a damage criterion based on the yielding and ultimate displacement points has been selected. These damage states describe an estimate of the combined structural, non-structural and contents damage of the building.
- The expected value of the natural logarithm of the displacement response (D) given the intensity measure level (IML), $\ln \eta_{(D|IML)}$, is modelled by the slope and intercept of the linear regression, and the probability of exceeding each damage state (P_{eDS}) is then calculated for a given level of intensity (IML) as follows, where Φ is the cumulative standard normal distribution function, DL is the damage threshold displacement for each damage state and σ is the standard error of the regression (which directly accounts for the record-to-record variability and has been increased to model the building-to-building and damage threshold variability):

¹ https://gitlab.seismo.ethz.ch/efehr/esrm20_exposure

$$P_{eDS} = 1 - \Phi\left(\frac{\ln(DL) - \ln\eta_{D|IML}}{\sigma}\right) \quad (1)$$

Within the SERA project, improvements to the above presented method for reinforced concrete buildings are being undertaken, as described in [13]. These improvements mainly address steps 1 and 2 of the methodology. Rather than defining capacity curves of SDOF oscillators using existing literature, a simulated design of moment frame and infilled frame reinforced concrete buildings with different numbers of storeys (between 1 and 6) is being undertaken for gravity loads as well as low, moderate and high seismic design under a range of lateral force coefficients between 0 and 30% (leading to 132 building classes). The variability of the geometrical and material properties is considered for each building class, leading to the simulated design of 150 buildings per building class. Numerical models (MDOF) of these designed buildings are then produced and pushover curves are undertaken in each direction to produce the capacity curves. These capacity curves are used to define the backbone of the hysteretic model of 2DOF systems in OpenSees and then the fragility functions are derived as described above.

Consequence models (also referred to as damage-to-loss models) are used to transform the fragility functions to vulnerability functions (that describe the distribution of loss ratios conditioned on a level of ground motion). The losses that will be considered in the European Seismic Risk Model will be direct economic loss due to structural, non-structural and contents damage (and thus the loss ratios will represent the ratio of cost of repair to cost of replacement of the buildings) and fatalities (and thus the loss ratios will represent the ratio of the number of fatalities to the number of occupants of the buildings).

Converting the fragility functions into economic vulnerability curves is performed with consequence models that provide an estimate of the mean ratio of the cost of repair to the cost of replacement for each damage state. Several analytical tests and evaluated claims data have shown that 5%, 20%, 60% and 100% seem to be realistic [12]. An approach that estimates the fatality risk from the probability of collapse of buildings is being used in the European Risk Model given that it has been observed in past earthquakes that the number of earthquake shaking casualties is driven by the number of buildings that fully or partially collapse, as this is directly linked to the percentage of occupants trapped in the building [15].

The fatality vulnerability model is defined as the mean probability of loss of life, given a level of ground shaking. Fatality models for each building class are being developed in SERA by combining the DS4 (i.e. complete damage) fragility functions ($P_{DS \geq DS4|IML}$) with the mean probability of loss of life, given DS5/collapse ($P_{LL|DS5}$) and the probability of collapse given that the damage reaches or exceeds DS4 ($P_{DS5|DS \geq DS4}$):

$$P_{LL|IM} = P_{DS \geq DS4|IML} \times P_{LL|DS5} \times P_{DS5|DS \geq DS4} \quad (2)$$

The mean probability of loss of life, given collapse ($P_{LL|DS5}$) for different building classes can be obtained from various empirical sources (e.g. [15]) and new models are currently being developed with fatality and damage data that has been provided by Pomonis (*personal communication*). The probability of collapse given DS4 is reached/exceeded can be obtained from damage databases such as the Da.D.O. database of building-by-building damage data from Italian events (http://egeos.eucentre.it/danno_osservato/web/danno_osservato) as well as the aforementioned empirical data. The Da.D.O. database provides a description of the extent of collapse to vertical, horizontal and roof elements of the buildings, and an investigation into which collapse mechanism correlates best with fatalities is being evaluated. Also, the influence of ground shaking intensity on the probability of collapse, given that DS4 is reached/exceeded is also being studied with these databases.

3. From Software to Model Testing

Taking inspiration from the four levels of software testing (see e.g. <https://www.seguetech.com/the-four-levels-of-software-testing/>), the tests of the European Seismic Risk Model (ESRM20) have been divided into the following four categories: unit tests, integration tests, system tests, and acceptance tests.

Unit testing: during this first round of testing, a computer program is typically submitted to assessments that focus on specific units or components of the software to determine whether each one is fully functional. For ESRM20 a unit test might, for example, look separately at the performance of the fragility, vulnerability or exposure components.

Integration testing: in this level of testing a number of units within a program are combined and tested as a group. Within ESRM20, an example of an integration test combining the exposure and vulnerability would be to estimate the losses from past events using ShakeMaps (with well constrained ground motions) to compare the estimated and observed losses.

System testing: this is the first level in which the complete application is tested as a whole. Within ESRM20, all of the outputs of the model (i.e. average annual losses at national and sub-national levels for residential, commercial and industrial occupancy types and national loss exceedance curves) will need to be calculated within reasonable run-times and the results will be initially sanity checked in terms of the ranking of countries within Europe.

Acceptance testing: the final level of testing is conducted to determine whether the system is ready for release. A workshop to investigate a wide range of results of the ESRM20 with an audience of experienced risk modellers (some of whom will also be end-users/stakeholders) is planned before the release of the model. Comparisons of the results will also be made against other initiatives that have covered European risk such as the Global Assessment Report [16], GEM's Global Risk Map v2018.1 [17] as well as national risk assessments (e.g. Italy's 2018 National Risk Assessment by the Department of Civil Protection: <http://www.protezionecivile.gov.it/documents/20182/823803/Documento+sulla+Valutazione+nazionale+dei+rischi/>) and insurance/reinsurance industry models (where available).

This paper focuses on the first two types of tests and discusses the way towards eventual prospective testing of the risk model, once system and acceptance testing has been undertaken and the model is publicly released.

4. Unit Tests

4.1 Exposure Model

The development of the exposure models relies on a number of different sources of data and expert judgment that are integrated to produce a final model. A number of tests of the final model are needed to 'sanity check' the integration of these different sources. A number of exposure metrics are automatically extracted from each country-based exposure model, such as the average population per dwelling, the average number of dwellings per building, the average dwelling cost, and ratios of the total replacement cost between commercial and residential, industrial and residential and commercial and residential buildings. It is expected, for example, that the residential building stock should have a higher total value than the commercial building stock which in turn should be higher than the industrial building stock. The other exposure metrics can either be checked against census data (when available) or outliers can be easily identified and corrected. Other sources that can be used to verify the exposure model include the residential, industrial and commercial capital stock values in the GAR [16] model as well as data on the GDP per sector for industry and services that can be found in online sources such as those provided by the World Bank or the national statistics office of each country.

4.2 Vulnerability Model

A unit test of the vulnerability models that is currently undertaken is relative comparison of the fragility between different construction materials and lateral load resisting systems and check whether it matches engineering judgment and observations from past European earthquakes. As an example, Figure 2 presents a comparison of the complete damage masonry fragility functions developed for European buildings using the GEM methodology, and it shows that the trend of fragility is as expected – the most fragile type of construction

is adobe, and the least fragile is the low code confined masonry. It is noted that as AvgSa is a sufficient intensity measure (see e.g. [18]), and thus allows direct comparisons between all building classes.

Fig. 2 – Example of the comparison of the complete damage fragility functions for different types of European masonry buildings

A comparison with a selection of the existing fragility and vulnerability functions that are being collected as part of the SERA project will also be carried out to ensure that the proposed models are in line with previous studies performed in Europe. However, differences with respect to past studies are expected given that many of the models in the academic literature have not been calibrated or tested using past earthquake damage and loss data. Hence, although comparisons with existing models is an important unit test, it is even more important to ensure that the proposed models are tested against empirical data. In order to compare the proposed vulnerability models for economic loss and fatalities for a given country with empirically derived models, a mean vulnerability function calculated through an exposure-weighted combination of all the building classes in the country is being undertaken. These vulnerability functions (in terms of both economic loss and fatalities) can then be compared with the empirical models developed by PAGER [19, 20]. The latter models are in terms of MMI and so, for comparison purposes, all analytical models have been estimated in terms of spectral acceleration at 0.3 s and converted to macroseismic intensity. The Faenza and Michelini [21] ground motion intensity conversion equation (GMICE) has been used and the mean and mean ± 1 standard deviation intensities have been computed. Figure 3 shows comparisons of the European analytical vulnerability models in terms of both economic loss and fatalities with PAGER's empirical models for Italy.

Fig. 3 – Comparison of the PAGER country-based economic (left) and fatality (right) vulnerability models with the current analytical European vulnerability models for Italy. The three dotted lines show the functions with the mean and ± 1 standard deviation of the ground motion intensity conversion equation.

This figure shows that the economic vulnerability models compare remarkably well with the empirical PAGER models, whereas the fatality models lead to lower estimations than PAGER. Similar findings for the economic loss have been found for Greece, whereas a slight overestimation of past fatalities has instead been observed. This test demonstrates that more focus needs to be placed on the European fatality model before proceeding to system and acceptance testing.

5. Integration Tests

5.1 Hazard curves and vulnerability models

The average annualized loss ratios (AALR) for a number of cities in Europe with different levels of hazard are also being computed. This is an integration test as it combines the hazard and vulnerability components of the risk model. Currently hazard curves have been computed using the ESHM13 model, but these will be replaced with the ESHM20 curves once they become available. This test can be used to identify excessively vulnerable (or excessively resistant) building classes. As an example, the comparison between the AALRs aggregated by macro-building classes (i.e. CR/LDUAL, CR/LFINF, CR/LFM, CR/LWAL, MCF, MR, MUR, S/LFBR, S/LFINF, S/LFM, S/LWAL and W – see GEM Building Taxonomy for definition [11]) is provided in Figure 4, for 3 locations in Europe with different levels of hazard (Vienna, Lisbon and Istanbul).

Fig. 4 – Comparison of AALR for different macro building classes in three cities in Europe

5.2 Ground motion, vulnerability and exposure models

Another integration test is planned to test the ground motion, exposure and vulnerability together through a ‘history check’. The total losses (fatalities and economic losses) estimated from all events in the EMEC earthquake catalogue since 1980 will be undertaken by randomly simulating ground motion fields using the latest European ground motion logic tree, and combining them with the European exposure and vulnerability models to estimate economic losses and fatalities. These results can then be compared with the total observed losses and empirically derived annual average losses and loss exceedance curves (with the losses adjusted to today’s value). Sources of loss data for this purpose include NatCatService database [22] for economic loss and Centre for Research on the Epidemiology of Disasters (CRED)’s EMDAT database [23]. It is important to note when carrying out these comparisons is that these disaster databases cover the entire built environment which include infrastructure impacts (and not just the residential, commercial and industrial buildings that are considered here).

5.3 Vulnerability and exposure models

In order to focus the integration tests on the vulnerability and exposure models, constrained ground motions from *ShakeMaps* or physics-based modelling of the ground motion from past events can also be undertaken. These tests might look at the statistics for a number of events (as in the test above) and a more detailed test for a single event can be performed.

5.3.1 Europe

The current European vulnerability and exposure models have been tested using damage and loss data from European past events between 1980 and 2017 from the NatCatService database [22]. In this process, USGS *ShakeMaps* were used with the European exposure dataset and the fragility and vulnerability functions in order to estimate the number of collapsed buildings and direct economic losses, respectively. The framework employed for these calculations is described in [24] and has been implemented in the OpenQuake-engine as the ‘Scenario from ShakeMap’ calculator. A number of randomly generated ground motion fields (considering spatial and inter-period correlation of the spectral ordinates) have been generated from the *ShakeMaps* and then these have been combined with the exposure and vulnerability to estimate the mean loss. A comparison between the estimated and observed losses (adjusted to 2017 values) is depicted in Figure 5. Although a fair agreement between the estimated and observed losses was obtained (with limited bias), there is clearly a large dispersion in the results. Reasons for this variability include differences in the exposure model and the actual built environment, bias in the collection of the observed damage and losses, and large uncertainty in the ground shaking due to lack of recording stations in the affected regions (e.g. [25]). In order to reduce these uncertainties, more detailed focus on specific events has also been undertaken, as described in the following sections.

Fig. 5 – Comparison between estimated and observed losses for over 20 past events in Europe using USGS *ShakeMaps*

5.3.2 Italy and Greece

In Italy, it has been possible to compare the estimation of damage using the European fragility functions with the observed damage in the 2009 L’Aquila and 2012 Emilia earthquakes due to the availability of the damage data for individual buildings in the Da.D.O database [26], as well as locally developed *ShakeMaps* by INGV (<http://shakemap.rm.ingv.it/shake/archive/>). The latter *ShakeMaps* include a local network of accelerometers and are thus expected to be better constrained than the USGS maps for this region. The damage data in the

Da.D.O. database needs additional processing before it can be used to test the analytical fragility functions as it does not include the undamaged buildings. The ISTAT census data from 2001 has been used to estimate the total number of reinforced concrete and masonry buildings in each municipality and then the number of damaged buildings from Da.D.O. has been removed to estimate the number of undamaged buildings. The same exercise has been undertaken for Emilia using the 2011 ISTAT census.

Exposure models for each event were thus developed and appropriate analytical fragility functions were mapped to the building classes in the models. The same framework described above for Europe has been used with fragility functions rather than vulnerability models. The results for L'Aquila and Emilia presented in Figure 6 show a slight underestimation of the highest damage levels. For L'Aquila both the INGV and USGS *ShakeMaps* have been used which show that the locally developed maps lead to be a better estimation of the damage. For the Emilia 2012 event, which was characterized by two close events of similar magnitude, a better estimation is made when the maximum ground shaking of the two events at each location of the exposure model is taken (identified by the results labelled 'max' in Figure 6). Figure 6 also illustrates the variability in the estimated damage in L'Aquila (using the INGV *ShakeMap*) due to the uncertainty in the ground motion.

Fig. 6 – Comparison of observed damage data (Da.D.O.) and estimated damage using the European fragility functions for L'Aquila 2009 (top left) and Emilia 2012 (top right). The variability in the estimated damage due to ground motion uncertainty is demonstrated for L'Aquila through a box and whisker plot (bottom). [DS0: no damage, DS1: slight, DS2: moderate, DS3: extensive, DS4: complete, DS5: collapse].

Similar tests of the European exposure and fragility models have been undertaken in Greece using the Thessaloniki 1978 and Athens 1999 events (see [27] for more details). Good comparisons between the modelled and observed damage have been found in both cases. For both scenarios, appropriate fault rupture models were used to estimate the ground shaking and were found to lead to better estimates of the damage distribution than the USGS *ShakeMaps*, as shown for example in Table 1 for the Thessaloniki 1978 earthquake.

Table 1 – Comparison of observed and estimated damage for the Thessaloniki 1978 earthquake

Damage State	Color Tag	Estimated damage - fault rupture model	Estimated damage – USGS <i>ShakeMap</i>	Observed damage – post earthquake tagging
No Damage	Green	78.2 %	92.2 %	74.5 %
Slight				
Moderate	Yellow	14.6 %	6.95 %	19.1 %
Extensive				
Complete	Red	7.2 %	0.85 %	6.4 %

6. Concluding Remarks

Testing of the European seismic risk model following the framework outlined herein will continue until the public release in October 2020. Subsequently, a number of activities that are being developed in the European RISE project (www.rise-eu.org) will lead to improved testing of the model in the future. One such activity includes the development of a European *ShakeMap* system that will use the tectonic regionalization, ground motion logic tree and site amplification of the European hazard model, which can then be used in the tests outlined above. Another activity relates to the setting up of a European testing centre for hazard and risk models (similar to the CSEP center in California, e.g. [28]). Once the ESRM20 is publicly released it will then be possible to design how the model (or its components) could be submitted for prospective testing.

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